

D2.1 Prospects and limitations of state-of-the-art seasonal-to-decadal climate predictions

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* **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent filings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
About ASPECT	6
1 Introduction	7
2 Skill Assessment	8
2.1 Detailed contributions of WP2.....	8
3 Extremes	10
3.1 Detailed contributions of WP2.....	10
3.2 Interactive tool to identify climate extremes.....	13
4 Combining s2d predictions and applications	14
4.1 Detailed contributions of WP2.....	14
5 Bridging timescales	14
5.1 Detailed contributions of WP2.....	14
6 Contribution to Super User projects	15
6.1 Applications for the wine industry.....	15
6.2 Applications for the pensions sector.....	16
6.3 Applications for the humanitarian sector (British Red Cross).....	17
6.4 Applications for the humanitarian sector (Save The Children International - SCI).....	18
7 Model deficiencies	19
7.1 Detailed contributions of WP2.....	19
8 Summary	20
8.1 Skill Assessment.....	20
8.2 Extremes.....	21
8.3 Combining s2d predictions and applications.....	21
8.4 Bridging timescales.....	21
8.5 Methodologies to account for model deficiencies in existing systems.....	21
References	23

Executive Summary

This Deliverable presents research conducted within the framework of ASPECT WP2 to advance our understanding of the sources of predictability in seasonal-to-decadal forecasts and to identify model deficiencies that critically impact forecast quality. By examining both the prospects and limitations of current prediction systems, these studies offer insights into where progress has been made and where challenges remain. Several of these studies have been published, while others have been submitted for publication, or are being finalized. To maintain the volume of this Deliverable reasonable, the results listed here are only indicative (intended as pointers). Nevertheless, they provide an overview of the diverse aspects that have been investigated using a wide variety of novel methodologies, such as the skill analysis of extremes, the combination of seasonal-to-decadal climate predictions, bridging timescales, and the support of user case studies.

About ASPECT

ASPECT aims to set up and demonstrate a seamless climate information (SCI) system with a time horizon up to 30 years and accompanied with underlying research and using climate information for sectoral applications. The project's goal is to improve existing climate prediction systems and to merge their outputs across timescales together with climate projections to unify a SCI as a standard for sectoral decision-making.

The project focus will be on European climate information, but we will also look where there is a wider policy interest (e.g., disaster preparedness) and in regions of European interest. We will maintain a strong link with the WCRP lighthouse activities to exploit learning for explaining and predicting earth system change. To provide a bandwidth diversity of information, the SCI system will be based on multi-model climate forecasts and will build on learning from projects such as EUCP. It will align with new activities on Digital Twins within Europe, including DestinE. The SCI will combine physical science aspects with those from other disciplines to ensure the information is robust, reliable, and relevant for a range of user-driven decision cases. The information package will incorporate baseline forecasts and projections (plus uncertainty), and will explore new frontiers (e.g., extremes which are of socioeconomic high-level interest).

To ensure success, the research will encompass: an understanding and attribution of various processes along timescales (such as exploring signal-to-noise ratio) and their impact on predictability, new ways of initialisation of the prediction systems, merging predictions with projections, provision of regional SCI for Europe by downscaling (statistical methods, AI) and HighRes models (including convection-permitting models) and innovative post-processing method enhancing the skill and robustness of the climate forecasts.

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents prospects and limitations of state-of-the-art seasonal-to-decadal climate predictions. On the one hand, the presented results highlight advances in understanding the mechanisms that contribute to predictability, improvements in forecast skill for specific variables and regions, and the potential for better anticipating extreme events. On the other hand, the findings underscore persistent challenges, including biases in model simulations, signal to noise errors, limited predictive skill in certain regions or time scales, and difficulties in capturing the complex interactions between climate components. By identifying these gaps, the studies point to areas where research and model development are needed to further enhance the robustness and usability of climate forecasts.

Skill Assessment: Our research evaluates the performance of operational climate prediction systems in simulating climatic anomalies and extreme events across various timescales. Notable findings include the improved skill of multi-year forecasts initialized in El Niño/ La Niña conditions and insights into the predictability of high-impact events such as the 2022 Pakistan floods. Studies also highlight the influence of oceanic variability on climate predictability, including the role of the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and Atlantic Multidecadal Variability (AMV) in seasonal and decadal forecasts.

Extreme Events: With the increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, our studies assess their predictability and influencing mechanisms. Our studies demonstrate significant decadal predictability for certain extremes, such as European summer heatwaves linked to the variability of the North Atlantic climate system. Further, studies explore the likelihood of unprecedented heat and drought events in the coming decades and the sources of predictability for droughts in Australia and spring frosts in Europe.

Model Deficiencies: A critical aspect of WP2 is the identification of systematic biases and limitations in climate models that impact prediction skill. For example, the *signal-to-noise problem* in NAO forecasts is found to relate to deficiencies in ocean–atmosphere feedbacks. Also, model errors in the representation of long-term trends are found to impact the predictive skill. Our findings suggest that improving model fidelity can enhance forecast accuracy and reliability.

Bridging Timescales and Applications: The project also focuses on translating seasonal-to-decadal predictions into actionable information for various sectors. Case studies illustrate the benefits of hybrid forecasting approaches and tailored climate services for industries such as agriculture and water management. Additionally, new experimental protocols aim to extend prediction horizons beyond the current decadal limits, bridging seasonal and decadal forecasting efforts.

Contributions to Super-User Case Studies: ASPECT WP2 actively collaborates with Super-User projects to ensure that climate predictions address real-world needs. Applications to the wine industry, water-resource management, and regional climate risk assessments illustrate how improved forecasts can support strategic decision-making and resilience planning.

Together, these results provide a nuanced view of the current state of seasonal-to-decadal climate prediction, emphasizing both its growing potential and the obstacles that must be overcome to improve forecast reliability and applicability. As the ASPECT project progresses, ongoing assessments about the usability of the innovative predictions with extended forecast horizons (multi-annual to multi-decadal) and interdisciplinary collaboration will further enhance climate predictions for decision-makers and stakeholders.

2 Skill Assessment

This work aims to assess the skill and capability of current operational prediction systems in realistically simulating and forecasting climatic anomalies and high-impact extreme events, which are crucial for developing effective adaptation strategies and climate applications. The evaluation spans multiple forecast horizons, from sub-seasonal to seasonal, interannual, decadal, and even extended decadal. Some findings offer useful insights for the interpretation and actionable use of forecasts, while other findings highlight the need for careful use and analysis of forecasts. A particular focus is placed on extreme events, including intra-seasonal variability, high-impact events, weather regimes, and compound or unprecedented events. We also strive to evaluate skills arising from internal variability and externally forced signals. By addressing these aspects, this assessment provides valuable insights into the strengths and limitations of current prediction systems, helping to enhance their usability for climate risk management and decision-making.

2.1 Detailed contributions of WP2

Perfect-model predictions and (to a smaller extent) also real-world hindcasts indicate enhanced skill in multi-year predictions initialised in El Niño or La Niña states compared to predictions initialized in neutral ENSO conditions. The results indicate that certain initial states provide increased predictability, revealing windows of opportunity for more skillful multi-year predictions. (BSC, Liu et al. 2023)

Figure 1: The mean squared skill score (MSSS) for the near-surface temperature in the perfect-model predictions for decadal simulations initialised in El Niño (EN; a, b, c), La Niña (LN; d, e, f), and the skill difference between the different groups: El Niño – neutral (g, h, i) and La Niña – neutral (j, k, l). Rows correspond to forecast year 1 (a, d, g, j), the average of forecast years 2–3 (b, e, h, k), and the average of forecast years 4–6 (c, f, i, l). The plus sign stippling indicates grid cells where the skill score or skill differences are significant at the false discovery rate (FDR) being 0.2 (when adjusting for the false discovery rate, see Methods for details). The square symbols indicate grid cells where the skill score or skill differences are significant at the 90% level (outside the 5%–95% confidence interval based on local individual testing with 1000 bootstrap realisations). (Figure from Liu et al. (2023).)

The Indian Ocean anomalous heating strengthens the polar vortex, while the tropical heating over the Pacific Ocean weakens the stratospheric polar vortex. Also, the impacts of Indian and Pacific tropical heating on the forecast probability for the NAO have different signs. The flow-dependent nature of the stratospheric pathway underscores the complexity of seasonal forecast predictability. (ECMWF, Senan et al. 2024)

On the role of the Pacific and North Atlantic Ocean for Rossby-wave propagation: our results show that the models represent an atmospheric response to the Rossby-wave source over the North Pacific, but its high- and low-pressure centers are displaced compared to ERA5. (SMHI, Fuentes-Franco, in prep.)

The unprecedented Pakistan floods of summer 2022 were very well forecasted. However, the average skill for summer precipitation is low ($r=0.27$), and hence the confidence associated with the 2022 forecast was not high enough for action to be taken. Further confidence could have been gained by examining the physical processes and realizing that the unusual summer La Niña conditions provided a window of opportunity to issue a more reliable forecast for extreme rainfall. (MetOffice, Dunstone et al. 2023)

Single-forcing historical experiments allow for better attribution. The North Atlantic “warming hole” is present in Historical, GHG-only and O3-only. A different —largely opposite— pattern emerges in Aer-only and Volc-only. Changing ocean currents are found to be key for the mechanism leading to the “warming hole”. The improved understanding of the causes of regional changes in climate is needed to attribute these changes to different internal and external drivers and to gain further confidence in the forecasts. (MPG, Pohlmann et al. in review)

Initialized predictions outperform uninitialized historical simulations in predicting Mediterranean precipitation in wintertime. Our study shows that this added value of initialization stems mainly from better representing the NAO variability. Implementing a hybrid dynamical–statistical model we achieve further improvements in predicting Mediterranean precipitation. Such simple hybrid models provide a way to account for the *signal-to-noise* problem in state-of-the-art forecast systems. Moreover, this hybrid approach can be used to provide improved, downscaled predictions. (CMCC, Nicoli et al., 2025)

3 Extremes

The likelihood of occurrence of weather and climate extremes has increased in the past decades. In addition, unprecedented and record-shattering extreme events will become even more likely in the next decades, posing a threat for various regions and sectors. The prediction of extreme events and their likelihood of occurrence for the next decade is therefore of fundamental importance for societal protection and for minimizing damages and losses. However, in the past, climate forecast skill assessment has addressed extreme events only in a few cases. With the availability of large ensembles of forecasts, also for novel forecast horizons, we here revisit the skill assessment of weather and climate extremes and high-impact events to make resilient statements about their occurrence and influencing mechanisms.

3.1 Detailed contributions of WP2

Extremes are, by definition, rare events and thus assessing and predicting their varying statistics is inherently difficult, even more so in a changing climate. Furthermore, realistically simulating extremes is a challenge for models. Nevertheless, it is exactly these rare extremes that are the most impactful events to society, raising the need for prediction. The frequency of occurrence, intensity and duration of extreme events is modulated by externally forced and internal climate variability, which is partly predictable. Recent studies show encouraging results on the decadal predictability of extremes (Figure 2). These studies also highlight the skill differences between initialised decadal predictions and uninitialised historical forcing simulations, helping to estimate the contribution of model initialisation and external forcings to prediction skill. (BSC, Delgado-Torres et al., 2023; CMCC, Tsartsali et al., in prep.)

Figure 2: Maps of ACC obtained with the DCP multi-model ensemble for the forecast years 1–5 (annual means) for the mean variables and extreme indices. The percentage of the global area with statistically significant positive or negative values is shown in the titles. The reference datasets used for the mean near-surface air temperature and PR are the GHCNv4 and the GPCC datasets, respectively. The reference datasets used for the temperature and PR indices are the BEST and REGEN datasets, respectively. Crosses indicate that the values are not statistically significant using a one-sided *t*-test accounting for autocorrelation and controlling the FDR with $\alpha_{FDR} = 0.1$. (Figure from Delgado-Torres et al. 2023).

Atlantic Niño SSTs at Yr-1 during boreal summer could be a possible predictor for the spring frequency of frost days (FFDs) at Yr-0. Better understanding of the sources of predictability helps to establish a meaningful seamless forecasting system for the end-users, which is currently in progress. Frequency of the FFDs is noted higher in March, while fewer events are in April, and in May. Lag correlation of FFDs shows a significant relationship with Atlantic Niño in the summer season. New simulations for the extended seasonal forecast runs from ECMWF (Yr-2) have been used to develop a seamless system. (UOXF, Abid et al. in preparation)

Blocking as a predictor of spring frosts. We present a statistical downscaling method which predicts variations in the frequency of occurrence of spring frost events in the important winemaking region of Catalunya at the seasonal timescale. (CMCC, Roncoroni et al., in preparation)

The European summer climate is influenced by decadal coupled variability in the North Atlantic. The so-called forced damped oscillation paradigm provides a plausible framework for understanding the coupled North Atlantic climate system on a 5–10 year timescale. Anomalies in North Atlantic heat content tend to precede extremely warm European summers for several years. Incorporating this coupled mode into predictions significantly enhances the forecast skill for European summer temperature and extremes. Specifically, an ensemble sub-selection that accounts for heat content anomalies leads to improved prediction skill for European temperatures and growing degree days (GDD). (MPG, Wallberg et al. 2024; MPG, Wallberg et al., 2025; MPG, Wallberg et al. in preparation)

Figure 3: Surface temperature predictions for summer (forecast year 3): Temperature anomalies in 2003 (1st row), 2018 (2nd row) and 2022 (3rd row) for ERA5 (1st column), the full ensemble mean (2nd column), and the selected ensemble mean (3rd column). Reference period: 1985–2014. (Figure from Wallberg et al. (in review).)

Assessing compound hot-dry extremes (HDSPI/HDSPEI) in decadal predictions. Hot-days are defined as days above the 90th percentile of maximum temperatures. Dry-days are defined as days falling in a month with SPI/SPEI ≤ -1 . A multimodel ensemble (MME) consisting of 12 models from CMIP6 DCP is used (125 ensemble members), for the initialization years: 1960-2009. The models show significant skill for compound hot-dry extreme events in the 2-5 years forecast range. Some limited added skill coming from the initialization of the forecast. However, most skills are still tied to the trend. (BSC, Aranyosy et al. under review)

Sources of decadal predictability of drought in southeastern Australia. We assess the decadal skill of summer drought in southeastern Australia, from 1961 to 2019, by using two drought metrics computed with the SPEI and SPI indices, and evaluate large-scale conditions linked with drought in ERA5 and model simulations (i.e. different constraints selecting projection ensemble members most similar to the observed climate variability state at the beginning of a forecast, DCP initialised decadal hindcasts and all CMIP6 ensemble members). We also assess how the model's initialisation affects the large-scale conditions, by comparing the variability-constrained and DCP ensembles with the All ensemble. Our study demonstrates that summer drought in southeastern Australia is predictable on decadal timescales, when constraining decadal variability with SST observations and with the state-of-the-art DCP ensemble. It also identifies large-scale drivers such as positive Interdecadal Pacific Oscillation (IPO) and negative Southern Annular Mode (SAM) phases as crucial drivers for drought occurrence, highlighting these teleconnections as areas where current climate models can be improved, especially for better capturing the positive IPO signal for enhanced future predictions. (BSC, De Luca et al., in preparation)

The North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre (SPG) plays an important role in climate predictability and influences climate variability. This study examines the impact of SPG SST variability on atmospheric circulation patterns and climate extremes. Anomalous SSTs in the SPG are found to induce an NAO-like atmospheric circulation response consistent with the concept of a positive ocean-NAO feedback (SMHI, Karami et al., in prep.)

Heat and drought extremes, typical for an end-of-the century climate, are predicted to occur already in the next decades. Year-after-year impact-relevant extremes go from virtually impossible to plausible in over two decades. Decades of end-of-century extreme heat in the near future are twice as likely if the North Atlantic is in a warm state. The results show that even under moderate warming, unprecedented levels of heat and drought stress typical of an end-of-century climate swiftly become a possibility over Europe in the near-term future. (ETHZ, Suarez-Gutierrez et al., 2023)

3.2 Interactive tool to identify climate extremes

A new interactive tool to identify climate extremes is being developed by the Met Office. DP3 ensemble mean standardized predicted rainfall anomalies for summer 2022 from 1st May initialized predictions are shown. Global land is split into 237 regions, 28 of approximately equal area (0.5 Mm²) with regional averages shown and green lines dividing regions. The regions with a $>\pm 2\sigma$ anomaly are highlighted by a thicker cyan border and the regions with a $> \pm 3\sigma$ are highlighted with a magenta border. On an interactive web version of this map, the user can 'click' on any region to open a dedicated webpage showing further information aimed at understanding the drivers and assessing forecast confidence, and a mask layer can be applied to only show those regions with statistically significant skill over the hindcast period. The tool is currently being evaluated using operational Met Office and ECMWF seasonal forecasts the results of which will be reported later. If successful, implementation in the C3S multi-model environment could be considered.

Figure 4: An interactive tool to identify climate extremes. DP3 ensemble mean standardized predicted rainfall anomalies for summer 2022 from 1st May initialized predictions are shown. Global land is split into 237 regions, 28 of approximately equal area (0.5 Mm²) with regional averages shown and green lines dividing regions. The 31 regions with a $>\pm 2\sigma$ anomaly are highlighted by a thicker cyan border and the four regions with a $> \pm 3\sigma$ are highlighted with a magenta border. On an interactive web version of this map, the user can 'click' on any region to open a dedicated webpage showing further information aimed at assessing forecast confidence (see text), and a mask layer can be applied to only show those regions with statistically significant skill over the hindcast period.

4 Combining s2d predictions and applications

A further step forward is to strive for the opportunities of prediction skill for applications. Clearly, the nature of skill assessment moves from purely physical interpretation of predictions towards user-defined, or combined metrics.

4.1 Detailed contributions of WP2

In developing climate services, there are cases in which what state-of-the-art climate predictions have to offer does not suffice in itself, e.g., because their forecast skill is found to be too low. This is particularly true when climatic anomalies are assessed at the local scale relevant to some applications (downscaled predictions needed). One way to go around such problems is to develop hybrid forecasting approaches blending dynamical predictions (model output) with statistical information derived from observations. (CMCC, Tsartsali et al., 2023, Nicoli et al., 2025)

Most products using decadal predictions provide information on multi-year average conditions. However, users are often interested in the probability of extreme conditions on shorter time-scales, e.g. seasons (rather than multi-year averages). A novel approach has been developed aiming to provide users with information on the probability of the occurrence of extreme seasons within a certain multi-year period (pooling). The approach is applied to a CMIP6 decadal predictions ensemble, suggesting that this ensemble is more skillful in predicting hot seasons in a 5-year period compared to a climatological forecast. (UOXF, Befort and Kruschke, in preparation)

5 Bridging timescales

ASPECT covers the timescales from seasons to 30-years, for which predictions and projections are available from to-date experiment design. Moreover, it has been recognized that interannual and multi-decadal prediction experiments complement the current approaches. This is an activity in WP1 and new experiments currently pursued there. Here, we illustrate that new opportunities for skill assessment can arise from these newly developed sets of hindcasts covering the multi-annual and beyond-decadal timescales. The assessment is ongoing and in cooperation with WP1.

5.1 Detailed contributions of WP2

Interannual protocol is established in WP1 and governs bi-yearly initialization (MAY, NOV), with lead times of minimum of 24 months, and minimum 20 members. The goal is to bridge seasonal and decadal predictions, which currently are limited either by having high samples of initializations with a seasonal scope, or low samples of initialization with a decadal time-scale. (Met Office, Dunstone et al. in preparation)

The protocol for "extended decadal" predictions requires the production of hindcasts initialized every 5 years from 1960 onward covering a forecast length of 20 years (minimum length) with a minimum ensemble size of 10 members. In all other details (e.g., use of forcings) the CMIP6 DCP-A protocol is followed. The last verifiable start-date is 2005 (arriving to Dec/2025). The goal is to examine the potential for having added skill stemming from initialization beyond the 10-year horizon of current decadal prediction systems and to provide an alternative to time-merging techniques in WP3. (CMCC, Athanasiadis et al. in preparation)

6 Contribution to Super User projects

The needs of key users in the ASPECT project on seasonal-to-decadal climate predictions is important for this deliverable (work package). Scientists from WP2 are involved in the Super User projects of ASPECT, and some examples are given below.

6.1 Applications for the wine industry

Information on the forecast quality and the sources of predictability and natural drivers for essential climate variables and indicators relevant for the wine sector is fundamental for the provision of climate services. ASPECT will go beyond hazard indicators and will co-explore other types of information considering specific magnitudes and thresholds, including risk-informed hazard indicators that result from a combination of climate-related variables and/or indicators.

Spring frost protection

Users need to know at seasonal timescales if they can apply management actions to delay bud-break and avoid major damages (e.g. pruning). At interannual-decadal timescales, users need to know if they should invest in frost prevention systems. The critical season for frost is spring. Just one night of frost (i.e., temperature $<0^{\circ}\text{C}$) can damage the whole production. This might lead to the death of the shoots. New shoots will appear with less fruit than the original ones (source: Codorníu).

Figure 5: ACC (left), RPSS for tercile categories (centre) and RPSS for quintile categories (right) obtained with the multi-model ensemble for predictions of Frost Days (days below 0°C) over Catalonia during March-April for the forecast years 1-3.

Potential Source of predictability for Spring frost risk

Seamless forecast protocol has been recently developed to forecast frost risk on multi-annual to monthly lead times for the vineyard users in the Catalonia region. We have noted May start date at 10-month lead time skilfully forecast the forthcoming March-April frequency of Frost Days (FFD). The level of skill is higher than any other start dates except that of lead time-0 start date. We noted a lag relationship of March-April FFD (0) with summer (-1) Atlantic Niño SSTs (ATL3 region). Large spread is noted among the ensemble members for summer ALT3 SST (-1) and FFD(0). The work is in progress to understand the pathways and mechanisms, which will help to increase the confidence on the level of skill noted with the May start date to forecast the frost risk during spring season.

Water management

User needs at seasonal timescales, if there are water restrictions, they might expect a lower production and decide to buy grapes from other producers. This will depend on the length and the intensity of the drought. At interannual-decadal timescales drought conditions may also impact the choice of other crops/varieties to be cultivated in the following years, selecting those with a lower water demand and more resistant to water scarcity. Codorníu (super-user) operates an irrigation system in the vineyards. In case of droughts, they will need to irrigate with the water available in the reservoirs.

6.2 Applications for the pensions sector

Inland flooding often commences following extreme precipitation. Skill in decadal predictions from the DCPPE ensemble for extreme precipitation across Europe is shown in Figure 6. There is not always significant skill, however, the residual correlation is significantly positive in some regions, pointing to an added value of model initialisation for predictions of extreme precipitation over those regions. This information has been shared with WP4 to aid them in the design of their climate service prototype for the pensions sector, and will help them advise which areas of Europe are likely to have more skill in decadal predictions (e.g. significant skill is shown in parts of Ireland, England, France, Sweden and the Balkan Peninsula). This information has been shared in a bespoke application for sharing plots within the project, using a Shiny App (https://earth.bsc.es/shiny/cdelgado_Extremes/ user: "extremes", password: "climateservices"), with the results published at global resolution (BSC, Delgado-Torres et al. 2023).

Figure 6: Spearman ACC obtained with the multi-model ensemble for the R95pTOT index (annual total precipitation when daily precipitation amount on a wet day exceeds the daily 95th percentile) for the forecast years 1-5. Left-top panel shows the skill obtained with decadal predictions. Right-top panel shows the skill obtained with historical simulations. Left-bottom and right-bottom panels show the skill comparison between decadal predictions and historical simulations through the ACC differences and residual ACC, respectively. Figure adapted from Delgado-Torres et al. (2023).

6.3 Applications for the humanitarian sector (British Red Cross)

The British Red Cross study is focussed on responding to high temperature events, such as when there might be heatwaves, especially when prolonged or severe, that require disaster responders to take actions like respond to vulnerable people in need, hand out water and provide rest centres.

WP2 have advised WP4 that seasonal skill is very low over the UK, especially for summer temperature. In Figure 7, we provide information from the DCPPE ensemble about decadal prediction skill for forecast years 1-5 for the TX90p index (percentage of days when daily maximum temperature exceeds the daily 90th percentile). There may be some positive residual correlation showing added benefit of the decadal prediction model, but this is not significant, and therefore pre-ASPECT decadal predictions may not currently add value to non-initialised historical simulations over the UK. WP2 also provided the information about the skill for the summer temperature, and also maps over Europe, to inform about the possibility for using decadal climate predictions in similar prototype climate services in other regions.

This information has been shared in a bespoke application for sharing plots within the project, using a Shiny App (https://earth.bsc.es/shiny/cdelgado_Extremes/ user: "extremes", password: "climateservices"), with the results published at global resolution (BSC, Delgado-Torres et al. 2023).

Figure 7: Spearman ACC obtained with the multi-model ensemble for the TX90p index (percentage of days when daily maximum temperature exceeds the daily 90th percentile) for the forecast years 1-5. Left-top panel shows the skill obtained with decadal predictions. Right-top panel shows the skill obtained with historical simulations. Left-bottom and right-bottom panels show the skill comparison between decadal predictions and historical simulations through the ACC differences and residual ACC, respectively. Figure adapted from Delgado-Torres et al. (2023).

6.4 Applications for the humanitarian sector (Save The Children International - SCI)

Medium to long-term climate change impacts due to heatwaves and desertification on food production as well as disease outbreaks following floods may affect child nutrition in various developing countries. In the short-medium term, SCI can develop climate-smart nutrition initiatives. In the longer term, drought conditions may impact the choice of crops to be planted in the following years, meaning that if a drought period is expected, selecting crops with lower water demand may be a smart choice. In the view of potential hazards exacerbated by climate change, impacts, and SCI's anticipatory action capacity, the initial design of the case study focuses on assessing the forecast quality of seasonal and (multi-)annual temperature and precipitation, and drought indicators. For instance, Figure 8 shows the quality of decadal predictions of mean temperature and drought conditions during the rainy seasons of Niger and Malawi for the forecast years 1-2.

Figure 8: Spearman ACC obtained with the multi-model ensemble for predictions of mean temperature (left) and the SPEI index (right) for the forecast years 1-2 over Niger (top) and Malawi (bottom). The predictions are aggregated for the livelihood zones, and tailored to the rainy seasons of the respective countries: JJAS and NDJFMA for Niger and Malawi, respectively.

7 Model deficiencies

A key objective of this work is to investigate how model deficiencies—such as systematic biases and the occurrence of extremes—interact and ultimately limit both the skill and usability of climate predictions. In this context, analyzing trends in hindcasts and their impact on user-relevant variables and predictive skill is essential. Furthermore, the misrepresentation of coupled processes and feedbacks plays a critical role in the signal-to-noise (S2N) problem, linking to model biases and the underestimation of the occurrence of extremes. Another focus is on assessing the ability of seasonal-to-decadal (S2D) predictions to capture observed trends and multi-decadal variability.

7.1 Detailed contributions of WP2

Investigating the value of trend correction in seasonal forecasts. Seasonal forecasts exhibit errors in the linear trend. Correcting the trend adds skill to seasonal forecasts. Comparing trend-corrected versus detrended forecasts helps to identify the forced signals. (ECMWF, Balmaseda et al. 2024)

Deficiencies in predicting the NAO have major impacts. Initialized decadal predictions (top panel) outperform uninitialized historical simulations in predicting winter Mediterranean precipitation up to 10 years ahead (middle panel). It is shown that this added value stems from better predicting the multi-decadal variability of the NAO. Thus, respective deficiencies in the DCP systems limit the skill over Europe (also for other variables and calendar seasons). (CMCC, Nicoli et al., 2025)

Ocean–atmosphere feedbacks key to NAO decadal predictability. The decadal prediction systems (DPSs) that exhibit significant skill for the NAO are those that on the one hand, have good skill for SST in the subpolar gyre area (Figure 9) and on the other hand are able to reproduce a more realistic SLP response to SST forcing (not shown). DPSs underestimate the positive feedback between the oceanic forcing in the subpolar gyre area and the NAO, this deficiency critically limits NAO skill (not shown). Therefore, improving the model's representation of ocean–atmosphere interaction and feedbacks is expected to lead to further improvements in NAO predictability and increase the signal-to-noise ratio in the forecasts. (CMCC, Patrizio et al., 2025)

Figure 9: ACC for SSTs. (Figure from Patrizio et al., 2025)

There is huge uncertainty in NAO projections, with some models showing an increase, others no change, and some showing a decrease. Some of the model differences can be explained by background water vapour and in particular the hygropause latitude relative to the jet. The standard multi-model mean is uncorrelated with observations. However, a constrained estimate is significantly correlated, but shows a signal-to-noise error. Calibrated projections that account for model differences and signal-to-noise errors suggest the multi-decadal NAO will increase to unprecedented values under a scenario with high concentration of greenhouse gases, likely to cause severe impacts including flooding and storm damage, but this can be avoided by mitigation. (Met Office, Smith et al. 2025)

8 Summary

D2.1 conducted presents the prospects and limitations of state-of-the-art seasonal-to-decadal climate predictions, aiming to enhance forecast reliability and identify key challenges. While the detailed analysis of prediction skill mechanisms will be addressed in a subsequent deliverable, the research conducted at this point provides valuable insights into both the strengths and weaknesses of current climate prediction systems. These studies assess the sources of predictability, evaluate model performance, and highlight critical deficiencies that impact forecast accuracy. In addition, the presented work addresses new frontiers of science in the area of seasonal-to-decadal predictions of extremes and high-impact events linking to project-defined Super User projects and providing new interactive tools for visualization. In fact, the close relationship between the assessment of climate forecast information and their utilization for end-users is demonstrated by a number of collaborations with the case studies in WP4. In a nutshell, the results of WP2 are the following:

8.1 Skill Assessment

- ENSO predictions are more skillful if initialized in El Nino or La Nina states compared to predictions initialized in neutral ENSO conditions
- The unusual summer La Nina of 2022 could provide a window of opportunity for predicting the Pakistan floods of that year
- Pacific provides a Rossby-wave source propagation in coupled models and emphasises its role for Rossby-wave propagation
- The NAO can now be skillfully predicted by some models
- The heating in the Indian and Pacific Oceans have flow-dependent imprints on the NAO and the polar vortex and underscores the complexity of seasonal forecast predictability.
- Role of AMV for decadal and multidecadal EU summer predictions
- Individual external forcings are examined for a better understanding of the sources of prediction skill
- The precipitation in the Mediterranean region is more skillful in initialized than in uninitialized predictions

8.2 Extremes

- Extreme temperature and precipitation are skillfully predicted on global scales for decadal timescales
- Complex extreme events (e.g. compound events) show significant skill in the 2-5 years range
- Heat and drought extremes, typical for an end-of-the century climate, are predicted to occur already in the next decades
- The coupled North Atlantic climate system is shown to have a pronounced influence on summer heat waves in Europe
- The SPG surface temperature variability has a profound impact on European winter climate and extremes
- Both, positive IPO and negative SAM are found precursors of droughts in SE Australia
- Atlantic Nino SSTs at Yr-1 during boreal summer is a possible predictor for the spring frosts in Catalonia, Spain
- Atmospheric blocking is found as a predictor of spring frosts in Europe

8.3 Combining s2d predictions and applications

- Hybrid forecasting approaches such as blending dynamical predictions (model output) with statistical information derived from observations make predictions more user relevant
- A novel approach has been developed aiming to provide users with information on the probability of the occurrence of extreme seasons within a certain multi-year period (pooling)

8.4 Bridging timescales

- Extended seasonal predictions are developed for bridging the timescales between seasonal and decadal predictions and jointly will be analysed with WP1
- Extended decadal predictions are developed for bridging the timescales between decadal predictions and climate projections and jointly will be analysed with WP1

8.5 Methodologies to account for model deficiencies in existing systems

- Model simulations are better able to predict the real world than themselves (signal-to-noise paradox, SNP). New work in ASPECT shows that the SNP applies to multi-decadal projections of the NAO.
- Deficiencies in predicting the NAO have impacts on predicting winter Mediterranean precipitation up to 10 years ahead
- Ocean–atmosphere feedbacks are key to NAO decadal predictability

- Calibrated projections that account for background water vapour and in particular the hygropause latitude relative to the jet are able to reduce uncertainties in NAO projections
- Correcting the trend in seasonal predictions leads to skill improvements
- A novel approach for drift correction in decadal and multi-decadal predictions has been developed

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